

An Empirical Correlation for the Calculated Effective Permeability For a Nonlinear Impulse Problem with a Simple Exponential Model for the Relative Differential Permeability

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Abstract

A nonlinear impulse problem is considered in which a simple exponential representation for the relative differential magnetic permeability is used to model the effects of a field dependent permeability (including magnetic saturation) on the performance of an electromagnetic shield subjected to intense pulsed electromagnetic fields. Previously, an analytical procedure was developed that characterized the maximum value of the transient electric field induced at the inner surface of the shield in terms of a dimensionless effective permeability that depends on a fundamental dimensionless combination of problem parameters. A series of finite difference time domain (FDTD) calculations was used to characterize the dimensionless effective permeability numerically for selected values of the dimensionless applied pulse parameter.

In this paper, a simple empirical relationship is presented that represents to very good accuracy the calculated effective permeability for the simple exponential permeability model. The relationship has only a single free parameter, yet it fits the numerical results to remarkable accuracy for values of the applied pulse parameter from zero to saturation. This relationship conveniently summarizes the nonlinearity of the problem for the maximum electric field.

Keywords

Nonlinear, ferromagnetic, permeability, shield, current, pulse, impulse.

INTRODUCTION

Ferromagnetic materials can provide good shielding due to their high magnetic permeabilities; however, the magnetic properties vary with the applied magnetic field and exhibit magnetic saturation at high field levels at which point the shielding performance drops dramatically. Predicting the performance of electrically conductive, ferromagnetic shields under intense pulsed electromagnetic field conditions is complicated because such materials exhibit nonlinear behavior. For example, due to the nonlinear behavior, the results at low field levels cannot be linearly scaled to

predict the results at high field levels as can be done with a constant permeability.

There is very limited analytical guidance concerning the nonlinear effects that ferromagnetic shields exhibit under intense transient field conditions because the governing partial differential equation is nonlinear. The analysis of such nonlinear problems is complicated by the lack of suitable analytical tools as exists in for the linear equation that arises in the case of a constant permeability.

In this study, a simple idealized relative differential magnetic permeability is used to investigate the nonlinear effects of a field dependent permeability, including saturation, on the salient features of an impulse problem. The simple model permits an additional nondimensional formulation for the problem beyond that for a generalized permeability model. The nondimensional formulation reveals how the various nonmagnetic and magnetic problem parameters enter into the solution even though the problem has not been solved. A dimensionless applied pulse parameter and a dimensionless effective permeability are defined that can be used to characterize the peak electric field response. Numerical calculations are used to evaluate selected points for the effective permeability curve corresponding to the differential permeability model.

Previously, preliminary numerical results for effective permeability data were presented. In this paper, a simple empirical representation is presented for numerical effective permeability data. The simple representation has only a single free parameter, yet it fits the numerical results to very good accuracy for values of the applied pulse parameter from zero to that for saturation. The relationship summarizes the nonlinearity of the problem and shows how the nonmagnetic and magnetic problem parameters affect the maximum value of the electric field transient. This nonlinear representation is an improvement over the linear theory using a constant permeability and the limiting nonlinear theory using a step magnetization curve.

DIFFERENTIAL MAGNETIC PERMEABILITY

For ferromagnetic materials, the relationship between the magnetic flux density B and the magnetic field intensity, H , is described by the magnetization curve, $B(H)$. In this paper, it is assumed that B is collinear with H . Hysteresis is neglected, and $B(H)$ is assumed to be a single-valued reversible function of H .

Definition of the Differential Permeability

There are a number of permeability definitions. The quantity of interest here is the field-dependent relative differential magnetic permeability, $\mu_{rd}(H)$, which is defined as

$$\mu_{rd}(H) \equiv \frac{1}{\mu_0} \frac{dB(H)}{dH} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where $\mu_0 = 4\pi \cdot 10^{-7}$ henry/meter is the permeability of free space. As the applied value of H is increased, $\mu_{rd}(H)$ typically starts at some initial value for $H=0$, increases to some maximum value, and then decreases to unity as the material undergoes saturation.

Differential Permeability Model

A simple idealized relative differential magnetic permeability is used to investigate the nonlinear effects of a field dependent permeability, including saturation. A simple magnetization model that exhibits saturation is

$$B(H) = B_s \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{H}{H_1}\right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where B_s is the saturation magnetization and H_1 is a characteristic value for the curve.

Substitution of Eq. 2 into the definition Eq. 1 gives a relative differential permeability model of the form

$$\mu_{rd}(H) = \mu_{ri} \exp\left(-\frac{H}{H_1}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where

$$\mu_{ri} \equiv \frac{B_s}{\mu_0 H_1} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

is the initial value of the differential permeability

$$\mu_{rd}(0) = \mu_{ri} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

The simple exponential relative differential permeability model given by Eq. 3 contains two independent parameters that can be used to model the relative differential permeability. For example, B_s and μ_{ri} can be specified while H_1 is determined by Eq. 4.

It is noted that this model includes saturation; however, it does not exhibit the appropriate limiting behavior for large H . For large H , the above magnetization curve exhibits the limiting behavior $B(H) \rightarrow B_s$ rather than the physical limit-

ing behavior $B(H) \rightarrow B_s + \mu_0 H$. Consequently, the relative differential permeability exhibits the limiting behavior $\mu_{rd}(H) \rightarrow 0$ rather than $\mu_{rd}(H) \rightarrow 1$ such that

$$\mu_{rd}(\infty) = 0. \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

PROBLEM FORMULATION

General Problem Statement

The general problem considered in this paper is the transient electric field induced along the inner surface of a long, thin-walled, cylindrical, electrically conductive, ferromagnetic shield subjected to an axially-directed, unipolar, short duration, surface current pulse along the outer surface. The current pulse leads to a transverse electromagnetic field condition at the outer surface. The problem configuration is shown in Figure 1. This general problem has practical application to cable shields and conduit shields subjected to short duration surface current pulses.

Figure 1. A thin-walled cylinder subjected to an axially-directed surface current pulse.

As the fields diffuse into the cylinder wall, a transient electric field is induced along the inner surface of the cylinder. For a surface current pulse that is of sufficiently short duration, the transient electric field response depends on the charge transported along the surface and is to a large extent independent of the particular time variation of the applied pulse. Such a pulse can be approximated by an impulse surface current, which leads to an impulse electric field response similar to that illustrated in Figure 2. The maximum value of the impulse response and the time at which the maximum value occurs are of primary interest.

Figure 2. Typical transient electric field response to a surface current impulse.

Planar Approximation

For a thin-walled cylinder, a planar approximation can be used, which simplifies the equation. The cylinder is approximated by a sheet of thickness, d , and conductivity, σ , while retaining the cylindrical boundary conditions.

For the planar approximation to the thin-walled cylinder problem the magnetic field intensity, $H(x,t)$, is described by the nonlinear partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial x^2} = \sigma \mu_0 \mu_{rd}(H) \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

subject to the initial condition at $t=0$

$$H(x,0) = 0, \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

an impulse surface current condition at the outer surface

$$H(0,t) = Q_0 \delta(t), \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where Q_0 is the charge per unit circumference that is transported along the outer surface of the cylinder during the pulse, and a vanishing field condition at the inner surface

$$H(d,t) = 0. \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

The electric field $E(x,t)$ at the inner surface ($x=d$) is evaluated from $H(x,t)$ by

$$E(d,t) = -\frac{1}{\sigma} \frac{\partial H}{\partial x} \Big|_{x=d} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

Problem with Exponential Permeability

Substituting from Eq. 3 into Eq. 7, the problem for the exponential permeability model becomes the nonlinear partial differential equation

$$\frac{\partial^2 H}{\partial x^2} = \sigma \mu_0 \mu_{ri} \exp\left(-\frac{H}{H_1}\right) \frac{\partial H}{\partial t} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

subject to the initial and boundary conditions given in Eqs. 8-10 above. The electric field is determined from Eq. 11.

DIMENSIONLESS PROBLEM FORMULATION

Previously, dimensionless problem formulation was used to deduce fundamental properties of the solution [1], [2].

Formulation for a General Permeability

In [1], an analytical procedure was developed to characterize the maximum value of the transient electric field response for the problem with a general permeability. It was shown that the maximum value of the electric field transient can be expressed in terms of an effective permeability that depends on an applied pulse parameter that is a fundamental combination of the nonmagnetic problem parameters.

The analytical procedure uses mathematical analysis supplemented with numerical calculations to characterize the effective permeability curve that corresponds to a prescribed differential permeability model.

For a general $\mu_{rd}(H)$, the maximum value of the electric field transient, E_{peak} , can be expressed in terms of an effective permeability $\mu_E(\beta)$

$$E_{peak} = 5.922053727 \frac{Q_0}{\mu_0 \mu_E(\beta) \sigma^2 d^3} \quad \text{Eq. 13}$$

that depends on an applied pulse parameter

$$\beta \equiv \frac{Q_0}{\sigma d^2} \quad \text{Eq. 14}$$

that is a fundamental combination of the nonmagnetic problem parameters (the charge per unit circumference, Q_0 , transported along the cylinder during the applied pulse; the electrical conductivity, σ , of the material; and the wall thickness, d , of the cylinder).

An analytical procedure was described that uses mathematical analysis supplemented with numerical calculations to evaluate the effective permeability for a prescribed value of the applied pulse parameter. E_{peak} is calculated for a prescribed set of problem parameters. Then, β is determined from Eq. 14 and $\mu_E(\beta)$ is determined from

$$\mu_E(\beta) \equiv 5.922053727 \frac{Q_0}{\mu_0 \sigma^2 d^3 E_{peak}} \quad \text{Eq. 15}$$

This allows the results for one set of problem parameters to be scaled to other problems with the same value of β . A series of calculations is used to characterize the effective permeability curve for a given differential permeability.

Formulation for Exponential Permeability Model

In [2], the simple exponential model in Eq. 3 was used for the differential permeability. For the exponential model, it was shown that the analytical procedure could be extended significantly. The effective permeability can be expressed in terms of a dimensionless quantity that depends on a dimensionless applied pulse parameter that is a fundamental combination of problem parameters that includes the saturation magnetization, B_s , as well as the nonmagnetic problem parameters. The evaluation of the fundamental curve versus the dimensionless applied pulse parameter required numerical calculations.

For the simple exponential differential permeability model, the applied pulse parameter is

$$\zeta = \frac{Q_0}{\sigma d^2 B_s} \quad \text{Eq. 16}$$

that is a fundamental combination of all of the nonmagnetic parameters and the magnetic parameter B_s .

It was shown that the effective permeability can be expressed as

$$\mu_E = \mu_{ri} \Omega_E(\zeta) \quad \text{Eq. 17}$$

where the quantity $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ depends only on the applied pulse parameter, ζ . That is, the ratio of μ_E to μ_{ri} depends only on the applied pulse parameter ζ

$$\frac{\mu_E}{\mu_{ri}} = \Omega_E(\zeta) \quad \text{Eq. 18}$$

Once $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ has been evaluated, the maximum value of the electric field is given by

$$E_{peak} = 5.922053727 \frac{Q_0}{\mu_0 \mu_{ri} \Omega_E(\zeta) \sigma^2 d^3} \quad \text{Eq. 19}$$

In [2], preliminary results of numerical calculations for $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ were presented. More precise calculations are presented here as well as a correlation for $\Omega_E(\zeta)$.

COMPUTATIONAL CONSIDERATIONS

Computational aspects for finite difference time domain (FDTD) solution of the nonlinear problem were considered in [3]. An implicit FDTD formulation with backward time differencing was used.

For the present calculations, the shield thickness was

$$d = 1 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m} \quad \text{Eq. 20}$$

and the electrical conductivity was

$$\sigma = 6.25 \times 10^6 \text{ S/m} \quad \text{Eq. 21}$$

Differential Permeability Representation

For high field levels, there are computational difficulties since the simple differential permeability model essentially vanishes rather than approaching the limiting value of unity. For this reason the differential permeability model that was used in the numerical calculations included the constant term of unity corresponding to the relative permeability of free space. This term is small compared to the initial relative permeability used in the calculations.

The relative differential permeability used was

$$\mu_{rd}(H) = 1 + \mu_{ri} \exp\left(-\frac{H}{H_1}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 22}$$

with

$$B_s = 1.07 \text{ T} \quad \text{Eq. 23}$$

$$\mu_{ri} = 8999 \quad \text{Eq. 24}$$

For these values of B_s and μ_{ri} , it follows from Eq. 4 that

$$H_1 = 94.61928498073560 \text{ A/m} \quad \text{Eq. 25}$$

Applied Pulse Representation

An applied pulse representation of the following form was used to approximate an impulse

$$H(0, t) = A_0 \left[\exp\left(-\frac{t}{t_f}\right) - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{t_r}\right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 26}$$

where A_0 is the amplitude factor, the time constant t_r is associated with the rise time, and the time constant t_f is associated with the fall time of the applied pulse ($t_r < t_f$). The peak of the applied pulse occurs at time

$$t_p = \frac{\ln\left(\frac{t_f}{t_r}\right)}{\frac{1}{t_r} - \frac{1}{t_f}} \quad \text{Eq. 27}$$

The charge per unit circumference that is transported along the outer surface during the applied pulse is

$$Q_0 = A_0 (t_f - t_r) C/m \quad \text{Eq. 28}$$

For the calculations considered here,

$$t_r = 2 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 29}$$

$$t_f = 2 \times 10^{-11} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 30}$$

$$t_p = 5.11685576220899041 \times 10^{-12} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 31}$$

The applied pulse duration was selected to be much smaller than the time for the maximum electric field.

Finite Difference Parameters

Spatial Increments

For all of the calculations, the shield was divided into 200 spatial intervals such that

$$\Delta x = 5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m} \quad \text{Eq. 32}$$

Time Increments

For computational purposes, the time domain was divided into three sectors.

The first time sector was from $t=0$ to the peak of the applied pulse ($0 \leq t \leq t_p$) for which the time increment was

$$\Delta t_1 = 2.555842788110449520 \times 10^{-18} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 33}$$

The second time sector was from the peak of the applied pulse to 100 time constants for the fall time ($t_p < t \leq t_f$) for which the time increment was

$$\Delta t_2 = 9.97441572118895505 \times 10^{-17} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 34}$$

The third time sector was from $100t_f$ onward ($>100t_f$) for which two values Δt_3 were used

$$\Delta t_3 = 1 \times 10^{-13} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 35}$$

for $A_0 \leq 8 \times 10^8$

$$\Delta t_3 = 1 \times 10^{-14} \text{ s} \quad \text{Eq. 36}$$

for $A_0 > 8 \times 10^8$. Due to computational difficulties, the results near saturation tend to be somewhat less precise than those for low pulse levels.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

As indicated above, a series of calculations is used to characterize the effective permeability curve for the differential permeability model. First, the transient electric field response is calculated for selected values for the amplitude of the applied pulse, A_0 , and the maximum value of the electric field, E_{peak} is determined. Then the applied pulse parameter ζ and the effective permeability μ_E are evaluated.

Peak Electric Field Results

The transient electric field response was calculated for selected values of A_0 while keeping other problem and computational parameters the same (except for Δt_3 for which two values were used). The results are shown in Figure 3. The transition to saturation can be observed near

$$A_0 = 1.85763888889 \times 10^9 \text{ A/m} \quad \text{Eq. 37}$$

for which $\zeta = 1/2$.

Figure 3. Peak Electric Field E_{peak} versus Applied Pulse Amplitude A_0 .

Effective Permeability for E_{peak}

For each value of the applied pulse amplitude A_0 , the applied pulse parameter, ζ , was evaluated using

$$\zeta = \frac{A_0(t_2 - t_1)}{\sigma d^2 B_s} \quad \text{Eq. 38}$$

Then, the effective permeability μ_E for E_{peak} was evaluated using

$$\mu_E(\zeta) = 5.922053727 \frac{A_0(t_2 - t_1)}{\mu_0 \sigma^2 d^3 E_{\text{peak}}} \quad \text{Eq. 39}$$

The results are shown in Figure 4. The calculated result for the initial value was

$$\mu_E(0) \cong 9000.62949653806 \quad \text{Eq. 40}$$

which is in good agreement with the expected result of 9000. The onset of saturation can be seen near $\zeta = 1/2$. Above $\zeta = 1/2$, the effective permeability approaches unity.

Figure 4. Effective permeability μ_E versus the applied pulse parameter ζ .

Estimation of $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ for E_{peak}

For each value of $\mu_E(\zeta)$ the value of $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ was estimated using

$$\Omega_E(\zeta) = \frac{\mu_E(\zeta) - 1}{\mu_{ri}} \quad \text{Eq. 41}$$

The calculated result for the initial value was

$$\Omega_E(0) \cong 1.0000699518 \quad \text{Eq. 42}$$

which is in good agreement with the expected result of 1.

EMPIRICAL CORRELATION FOR $0 \leq \zeta < 1/2$

It was found empirically that to a very good approximation, $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ can be represented over the range $0 \leq \zeta < 1/2$ by

$$\Omega_E(\zeta) \cong C(1 - 2\zeta)^a \quad \text{Eq. 43}$$

A comparison of results is shown in Table 1 and Figure 5.

Table 1 Comparison of numerical results for $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ with correlation $\Omega_E(\zeta)=C(1-2\zeta)^\alpha$.

ζ	$\Omega_E(\zeta)$	$\Omega_E(\zeta)=C(1-2\zeta)^\alpha$
0.0000000000	1.0000699518*	1.0000699518
0.0269158879	0.9523136410*	0.9539012909
0.0538317757	0.9050187541*	0.9073477365
0.0807476636	0.8578405421*	0.8603825338
0.1076635514	0.8106057295*	0.8129752180
0.1345794393	0.7631876950*	0.7650908070
0.1614953271	0.7154577191*	0.7166887459
0.1884112150	0.6673050377*	0.6677215000
0.2153271028	0.6185858795*	0.6181326369
0.2422429907	0.5692070187**	0.5678541490
0.2691588785	0.5189095440**	0.5168025975
0.2960747664	0.4675148082**	0.4648733600
0.3229906542	0.4147607631**	0.4119316631
0.3499065421	0.3603221480**	0.3577978136
0.3768224299	0.3037942860**	0.3022210767
0.4037383178	0.2446799706**	0.2448288030
0.4306542056	0.1823910523**	0.1850125623
0.4575700935	0.1163274635**	0.1216094084
0.4844859813	0.0467800260**	0.0514923249

* $\Delta t_3=10^{-13}$ ** $\Delta t_3=10^{-14}$

Figure 5. Comparison of numerical results with correlation $\Omega_E(\zeta)=C(1-2\zeta)^\alpha$ for $0 \leq \zeta < 1/2$.

$$C = \Omega_E(0) = 1.0000699518 \quad \text{Eq. 44}$$

and

$$\Omega_E(1/2) = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 45}$$

it was found that

$$\alpha \cong 0.85416314 \quad \text{Eq. 46}$$

The correlation Eq. 43 has only a single free parameter, α , yet it fits the numerical results for $\Omega_E(\zeta)$ to remarkable accuracy. Statistically, the correlation coefficient was found to be $r^2=0.999926797$, where $r^2=1$ would be perfect.

It can be reasonably expected that in the limit

$$\Omega_E(0) = 1 \quad \text{Eq. 47}$$

and the maximum electric field would be given by

$$E_{peak} \cong 5.922053727 \frac{Q_0}{\mu_0 \mu_r \sigma^2 d^3 (1-2\zeta)^\alpha} \quad \text{Eq. 48}$$

CONCLUSIONS

For the simple exponential permeability model given by Eq.3, it was found empirically that to a very good approximation the effective permeability for the maximum electric field for the impulse problem can be represented over the magnetically active range $0 \leq \zeta < 1/2$ by the simple correlation given by Eq. 43.

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